

SHORT NOTES

Thorium and Molybdenum Complexes with Myricetin

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Myricetin (I) is a 5, 7, 3', 4', 5'-pentahydroxyflavonol and its reaction with zirconium has been studied by Hörhammer *et al.*¹. Being a flavonol, it forms a stable complex with zirconium, replacing hydrogen of the 3-hydroxy group in conjunction with carbonyl oxygen.

Myricetin has been found to form deep yellow complexes with thorium and molybdate ions. In the present communication, the studies have been made on the complexes in 40% ethanolic medium in which these are quite stable. The use of ethanol is necessary to avoid precipitation of the reagent.

Procedure.—Myricetin was isolated from a natural source (private communication from S. K. Krishnan). Its standard solution was prepared in ethanol. Thorium nitrate and ammonium molybdate were used to prepare salt solutions, standardised by gravimetric methods.

A Unicam SP 600 and a Perkin Elmer spectracord were used for absorbance measurements and a Metrohm pH-meter, type E-350, was used for pH measurements. pHs of the solutions were adjusted with dilute solutions of NaOH and HCl.

Thorium Complex

Absorption spectra of myricetin and its thorium complex were taken at different pHs, using aqueous ethanol as blank. Net absorption spectra of the complex were obtained by subtraction of the readings in the two types of curves. Some of the representative spectra are shown in Fig. 1. It is evident that $\lambda_{\max}$ shifts from 410 m μ to 430 m μ with increase in pH from 2.0 to 4.0. This may be due to formation of different complexes though having same stoichiometric ratio of metal and the ligand. The absorption due to the reagent becomes insignificant beyond 440 m μ . Below 440 m μ , absorption due to the reagent is appreci-

able and it is necessary to use the corresponding solutions of the reagent as blanks. The studies of the complex have been carried out at 420 $m\mu$.

FIG. 1: Curve 1—4.5 ml myricetin ($M/2500$); pH 2.0.
 Curve 2—0.5 ml Th^{4+} ($M/2500$) + 4.5 ml myricetin ($M/2500$); pH 2.0.
 Curve 3— 2—1.
 Curve 4—0.5 ml Th^{4+} ($M/2500$) + 4.5 ml myricetin ($M/2500$); pH 2.8, using reagent as blank.
 Curve 5—0.5 ml Th^{4+} ($M/2500$) + 4.5 ml myricetin ($M/2500$); pH 4.0, using reagent as blank.
 In all cases solutions were diluted to 12.5 ml.

FIG. 2. Determination of composition of thorium-myricetin complex by Job's method.

No appreciable variation in optical densities of the reagent at 420 $m\mu$ from pH 2.0 to 4.0 was observed. The absorption due to its thorium complex is, however, affected by variation in pHs. The intensity is maximum at pH 2.0 and then it decreases. From pH 3.0 onwards, the absorbance increases again. The solutions were stable and no appreciable change in intensity was noticed for several hours.

The composition of thorium complex has been ascertained by the method of continued variations² at different wave lengths and pHs. Some of the typical curves have been plotted in Fig. 2. It is clear that at all pHs, the complex contains thorium and the flavonol in the molecular ratio of 1:1. The approximate value of stability constant of the complex has been calculated from Job's curves at pH 2.0 and at 420 $m\mu$. The value comes out to be 3.58×10^4 (at 20°).

2. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **2**, 9, 113.

Molybdenum Complex

In the case of molybdenum-myricetin system, several solutions were prepared containing molybdate solution (0.5 ml of $M/5000$) and myricetin (4.5 ml of $M/5000$). The pH s of the solutions were adjusted (from 1.0 to 6.8) and these were finally diluted to 12.5 ml, keeping 40% ethanolic medium. Absorption spectra of the solutions were taken against the reagent blanks, made in the same way, replacing molybdate solution by water.

The spectra reveal λ_{max} at 422 $m\mu$. In another set, to a fixed amount of molybdate solution (2 ml of $M/5000$) were added varying amounts of myricetin (0.5, 1.0...5.0 ml); the solutions were diluted to 12.5 ml after adjusting pH 2.4 in each case. The spectra plotted (Fig. 3) using the reagent blanks show λ_{max} at 422 $m\mu$.

FIG. 3 Absorption spectra of molybdenum-myricetin complex

The effect of changing H^+ -ion concentration of the system has been investigated from pH 1.0 to 6.8. The absorption by the complex was found to be maximum and almost constant between pH 1.5 and 2.5. Below pH 1.5 and above 2.5, it markedly decreased.

By Job's method at different pH s, the composition of the complex was found to contain the molar ratio of 1:1 of molybdenum and myricetin between pH 1.0 and 2.5. Above pH 2.5, there is a possibility of formation of a lower complex (metal—

ligand ratio, 2:1). This appears to be due to the presence of two chelating centres in the ligand molecule, viz., 3-hydroxy group in conjunction with carbonyl group and two *ortho*-hydroxy groups in B ring of the molecule. Molybdenum is known to form coloured complexes with two *ortho*-hydroxy groups present in aromatic compounds³. Average value of stability constant of 1:1 complex has been deduced from Job's curve at pH 2.0. It has been found to be 4.2×10^4 (at 20°).

The authors are thankful to Prof. T. R. Seshadri, F. R. S., for his encouragement and to Mr. S. K. Krishnan for his help in isolating myricetin. Two of them (B. P. G. and M. K.) are also thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of fellowships.